

Academic Research on the Importance and Place of Education in Economic Growth and Development Plans in Turkey

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Abstract

One school of thought contends that the phrases "economic growth" and "development" may be used interchangeably without loss of meaning. In spite of the fact that these two concepts are sometimes confused with one another, economic growth and development are both essential to the broader process of raising a society's quality of life (Unay, 1982). When we talk about "economic growth," we're referring to a gain in production capacity as well as actual output, and as a result, the quantity of national revenue (Dinler, 2005). On the other hand, development refers to a change in both thought and mentality as well as in the socioeconomic structures of a society; it also includes an increase in investment, the development of modern technologies, an increase in productivity, an increase in real income, and an increase in the level of education (Ozguven, 1988). The expansion of persons with higher levels of education is another part of development. According to McMahon (1999), education is one of the most essential contributions to the efficient functioning of economies and the broad adoption of the most recent technology because of the critical externalities that it delivers. In a society in which the majority of the population has achieved high levels of education, democratic institutions are in a better position to operate effectively and so have a greater chance of succeeding. When there is an elevated level of educational achievement in a culture, there is also a similarly low level of the frequency of violent and property crimes. Because of this, there is a decrease for money that is spent on judicial services and internal security. Therefore, when the educational level of the poor improves, the amount of money that is transferred to them in the form of transfer expenditures such as helps such as food, health, education, and unemployment benefits starts to diminish. The reason for this is because as low-income people get more education, their income levels also start to climb, which is a cyclical relationship. People who have finished their education tend to make decisions about their health with a better level of information and prudence as compared to those who have not. The ability of people with greater levels of education to make fair tax payments grows in a manner that is directly proportional to the growth in incomes of those with higher levels of education. Because it serves as a mechanism for the equal distribution of income and plays a role in promoting economic progress,

development, and financial stability, this kind of spending is often referred to as investment spending.

Keywords: *Economic Growth in Turkey, Development in Turkey, Development Plans in Turkey, Importance of Education in Turkey*

1. Introduction

Research and development expenditures are often referred to as research and development expenditures because they serve as a mechanism for the fair distribution of revenue. Research and development expenditures may also be referred to as R&D expenses (Mutlu, 1998). In many of the strategies being considered for Turkey's long-term economic growth, education is being treated as a top priority. The fact that planning in Turkey is seen as both a necessity for the public sector and a direction for the private sector is the defining characteristic of Turkey's approach to urban design. This can be summed up as the phrase "planning in Turkey is both a necessity for the public sector and a direction for the private sector." According to Kucuker (2008), the compilation of development plans became the normal operating practice in a considerable number of nations following the conclusion of the Second World War. Since 1963, Turkey's growth plans have been produced and put into operation every five years, with the exception of the most recent plan for Turkey's development, which was only recently implemented. With the help of this research, an attempt was made to investigate the role that education plays in Turkey's overall development aims (9th Development Plan). This investigation was conducted within the context of the goals and difficulties outlined in the development plans with reference to the idea of public goods and education. In particular, the aforementioned study was carried out with the plans' indicated objectives and difficulties serving as its background. Because of this, education and training in Turkey shown a totally unanticipated development throughout the anticipated time period (Güven, 1995). As a direct consequence of this, the legitimacy of the judicial system came into doubt, at least to some degree.

2. The Role of Educational Institutions in Society

When seen through the lens of Goods Theory, the idea of the public good was not brought up until 1739, when David Hume's Treatise on Human Nature was made available to the public for reading. This event took place thirty years prior to Adam Smith publishing his book. Samuelson's writings from 1954 and 1955, which are the basis of this theory, supplied the theoretical context for its development (Cornes and Sandler, 1996). Economists such as

Musgrave, Sax, Ugo Mazzola, Pantaleoni, and Knut Economists like as Wicksell, Buchanan, Malkin, Wildavsky, Kaul, and Mendoza made significant contributions to the debate of this issue during the course of the subsequent years (Goker, 2008; Turan, 2008). In their own works, Goker (2008) and Turan make reference to the works of the aforementioned economists (2008). The concept of "public goods" may be used to refer to a variety of distinct categories of products, such as club goods, completely public and semi-public goods, virtuous and non-virtuous commodities, and others. In order for a product or service to be acknowledged as a true contribution to the common good, it must be difficult to disassemble it into its individual parts; in other words, it must be indivisible.

In addition, it should be difficult to price or sell the item since its usefulness cannot be divided into segments; in addition, no one should be prevented from receiving the advantage it provides, and there should be no rivalry in the consumption of the commodities (Pehlivan, 2009; Turan, 2008). As a direct consequence of the decisions that have been taken about public policy, the following provisions for public goods have become increasingly prevalent. The provision of non-competitive goods and the supply of non-exclusive commodities are the two primary characteristics of public goods, and the examples given below are based on these characteristics. When one looks at the graph in more depth, one can see that the education service is highlighted a total of three times. It takes place in the fourth quarter because the training may be done at anytime and anyplace. It ranks in the third quartile because educated persons contribute to the production and economic well-being of the country (Kaul and Mendoza, 2003).

Economists who were linked with the Keynesian and Classical schools of thought continued to debate the proper role of the state in the education system, as well as how educational services and resources should be divided and employed (Oztürk, 2005). Keynesian economists saw funding for educational institutions as an expenditure on a "quasi-public benefit." Because of the broad adoption of the concept of an interventionist state that appeared as a direct consequence of the economic crisis that occurred in 1929. In addition to this, they emphasized the idea that the provision of education ought to be within the purview of the state. According to the Keynesian interpretation of economics, the state has taken on significant obligations in a variety of domains, including education, healthcare, housing, benefits for children, retirement due to old age, and unemployment insurance. These aspects include retirement owing to old age, education, health care, housing, and financial aid for children. The amount of money spent on education as a percentage of the overall amount spent by the state has lately begun to grow, which is a direct consequence of this situation (Oztürk, 2005).

The following is the term "development," which defines the ideal state that should be in every area of the life of a civilization, and its most thorough definition is as follows: (Amazigh, 2006). According to Eroğlu (2001), in order for a country to advance in terms of industrialization and development, there should be prerequisites in place first. These prerequisites include a political climate that is consistent and stable, improved transportation facilities, a favorable communication and financial environment, and a level of education that is adequate. These requirements are as follows:

For a country to advance in any way, certain conditions must first be met. The term "development planning" refers to the process of managers using available resources efficiently to bring about desired changes in a nation's economic, social and political climate in line with society's goals and objectives (Özer, 1999).

Long-term development policies are arranged according to a set of criteria that have been developed in advance in order to accomplish this aim. It is possible to claim that the first planning studies in Turkey were conducted between the years 1933 and 1950, and the foundations of the planned development strategy were built towards the end of the 1950s (Kücüker, 2008). This is something that is possible to say. Because it is conceivable to declare that the first planning studies in Turkey were conducted between 1933 and 1950, this is something that may be asserted. Since the 1950s, the idea of progress has been linked to the escalation of economic expansion. However, despite the fact that since the 1950s it has been associated with economic growth, the progressive process emphasizes the social aspect of this idea (Battal, 2011). Since the 1950s, this idea has been connected to the advancement of research into the study of growth. The concept of generating and enacting Development Plans appeared as a method of both guiding the economy in line with its natural flow and interfering by the economy's own logic. This was conducted via the creation and implementation of Development Plans (DPT, 2009). Beginning the development of these strategies in advance is something that is strongly encouraged. The State Planning Organization (DPT) was set up as a result of the adoption of the legislation on September 30, 1960, and it thereafter became subordinate to the Prime Ministry. The day we are celebrating marks one year when the legislation was first put into effect. The notion of a "social state" was incorporated as one of the distinguishing characteristics of the state in the Constitution, which was ratified in the year 1961. In addition, the Constitution of 1961 had planning restrictions, and the legislation that resulted from these regulations set up the legal foundation for planning. The commencement of research on the education planning process in Turkey corresponds with the beginning of the

execution of a planned development strategy. This is significant since the two processes are intertwined. According to Kucuker (2008), one of the instruments that are considered to be included in development plans to promote economic and social development is a medium-term five-year plan. Other tools that are considered to be included in development plans include long-term and significant perspective plans.

This was done in order to provide assistance to the targeted. The first two development plans, which covered the years 1963-1977 and were meant to span a period of 15 years, were constructed. These plans were prepared by the strategy that was described in the First Perspective Plan.

3. Futures Perspective Plan

On the other hand, due to the fact that this perspective plan was not fully implemented, a brand-new long-term perspective plan was developed in 1973 to cover the years 1973-1995. This plan covered the period from 1973 to 1995. It was supposed to span the years ranging from 1973 all the way up to 1995. This perspective plan served as the foundation for the development of the third and fourth plans for the organization's future, which were both based on those plans. Following the year 1980, there was a transition from central planning to strategic planning; thus, the execution of this perspective plan was restricted to just a part of its first scope. As a result of the transition from centralized planning to strategic planning, the scope of the plan as it was first conceived was constrained. One of the first tangible restrictions to decrease the efficacy of the state and planning in the economy was included in the Constitution in 1982, which was ratified in 1982. In 1982, a decision was made to enact this rule. In the Constitution of 1961, the fundamental obligations of the state included planning; however, the planning clause was shifted to the section on economic needs in the Constitution of 1982 (Kucuker, 2008). This was done in order to make room for new economic requirements. This was one of the first real steps that was done in an effort to lessen the impact that the government and economic planning had on the economy. With the publishing of Decree Law No. 641 in 2011, the Undersecretariat of the State Planning Organization (DPT), which had been in operation since 1960, was reorganized as the Ministry of Development. 2011 saw the passing of this legislation into law. The Ministry has begun to fulfill the responsibility for the SPO's development mission, which has been a part of its mandate ever since the SPO was established. Article 147 of the Decree-Law on the Amendment of Certain Laws and Decrees in Order to Adapt to the Amendments Made in the Constitution No. 703 mandated a rebranding of the Ministry of Development as the Ministry of Industry and Technology. This was done in order

to reflect the changes that were made to the Constitution. 2018 is the year of publication. The year 2018 saw the passing of this legislation. The changes that were made to the Constitution led to the adoption of this amendment. In 2018, the Presidential Decree No. 13 on the Organization of the Strategy and Budget Presidency was published in the Official Gazette No. 30488. This decree re-entrusted the Strategy and Budget Presidency with the responsibility of formulating a strategy for the country's future growth. The year 2018 was the year that both of these newspapers were first published. Because of this, it is reasonable to assert that the degree of connection between education and the expansion of the economy is one of a reasonably high strength (Taş, 2007). A statement to the effect that "Education is one of the most effective tools of development" was included in the First Development Plan. The first Development Plan said that "Education is one of the most effective instruments of development," which makes sense given that one definition of development is "the attempt to attain a desirable life order." According to Kücükler (2008), the significance of obtaining an education was underlined throughout the discussion. Research that takes an in-depth look at the Turkish education system and produces conclusions based on those results is what the organizations referred to as National Education Councils handle performing as part of their role in defining Turkish education. These studies, in addition to being of critical significance for the evolution of education in Turkey, are also accessible to a variety of viewpoints that are developed outside of official educational institutions. Although councils should serve as an institutional structure that will contribute to the formation of education policies in Turkey by making scientific and social decisions about education, they have taken their place in our educational life as a structural organization that puts forward suggestions. This is despite the fact that councils should serve as an institutional structure that will contribute to the formation of education policies in Turkey. In spite of this, councils should function as an institutional framework that will help to the formulation of education policy in Turkey by making judgments regarding education based on scientific and social considerations. Unfortunately, despite the fact that councils in Turkey are supposed to operate as part of an institutional framework that contributes to the creation of education policy, this is not the reality. (Deniz, 2001). Kılıç and Güven (2017) state that ever since they were founded, councils in the Turkish Education System have functioned as an advisory body (Kılıç and Güven, 2017). This organization handles directing education and making significant decisions about education. The assemblies' roles as institutions that steer education and make significant choices in the area of education have a rich and illustrious history. This history spans decades. National Education Councils are

"planning organizations," as said by Accountcolu (2001), who also refers to council judgments as "educational planning documents" (as referenced in Kücükler, 2008).

4. Besides the Legal Basis of National Education

In addition, Accountco-lu is of the opinion that the National Education Councils have the complete responsibility of addressing, debating, and guiding the general public. At the same time, the "Education Organization Legislation No. 2287," which is the foundation law of educational institutions, went into effect on the same day that it gave birth to the Education and Training Department, as well as the day it gave birth to the legal basis of the National Education. Additionally, this statute set up educational institutions (Aslaner, 2008; Deniz, 2001). As a direct consequence of this, the highest advisory body of the Ministry of National Education was set up for the purposes of directing the national education system, deciding the issues that are associated with education, conducting research on these issues, and finding potential solutions. The following are some of the reasons behind this: (Deniz, 2001). According to the laws, it was agreed that the future assembly meetings would take place once every three years. Additionally, it was decided that the first assembly meeting would take place in 1935. Both of these decisions were made in line with the law. Despite this, the first gathering of the assembly took place in 1939 for a variety of reasons, some of which were linked and others of which were not. As of the end of the calendar year 2014, a total of 19 sessions of the National Education Council has been completed. An in-depth analysis of these policy papers, which play a significant part in formulating education policies and may serve as a foundation for further research, will supply light on policy processes that include many stakeholders. These guiding papers for policy play a significant role. It has the potential to make a significant contribution to the process of formulating educational policy and laying the groundwork for further study. In this regard, the purpose of the research is to prepare for and take part in the National Education Council meetings that are scheduled to take place during the time period in which the projected development is scheduled to take place. The aim of this activity is to conduct an investigation into the factors that influenced the choices that were taken within the bounds of the educational policy decisions that were included into the development plans. In this investigation, the data sources that were used included ten papers about the zoning plan and thirteen documents about the National Education Council that were created within the time frame that was anticipated for the development process. During this period, both sets of papers were finished being worked on. This study will supply a foundational grasp of the subject matter and set up the groundwork for further research in the future. It is to examine the choices

that were made by the National Education Council during the planned development period and the decisions that were made in the development plans together, and to conclude whether or not these decisions are consistent with each other. The purpose of conducting this review is to establish whether or not these choices are consistent with one another. The demanding situation that the research model finds itself in at the moment. The study that was discussed before made use of the method of document analysis, which is one of the qualitative research methodologies that are useful to researchers. Analysis of textual documents that give information about events or circumstances that need to be researched is included in this method (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2002). These documents supply information about what needs to be studied.

When doing document analysis, the very first step that you need to take is to gather all of the pertinent papers. It is necessary to carefully study and process the relevant texts in their entirety before continuing with the analysis. According to Yıldırım and Şimşek (2008), the process of interpretation and assessment is conducted at the very last stage of the research. Manuscripts and printed materials make up the vast bulk of the resources that are used in research initiatives that are linked to document analysis within the realm of education (Duffy, 2014). Instruments for the Accumulation of Data The primary data source for this investigation is the actual written texts that have been analyzed. It is made up of 10 different five-year development plans (BYKP) that were produced throughout the planned development era and thirteen different National Education Councils that were held after 1962 to serve as data sources.

5. Planned Development Period

During the era appointed for planned development, each of these councils and plans came into being. In order to get access to the aforementioned papers, a web search was carried out on the websites of the Strategy and Budget Department of the Presidency of the Republic of Turkey and the Board of Education and Discipline. Given that the papers in issue were gotten from the proper governmental authorities, there is no circumstance that may lead one to dispute the legitimacy of the documents that are in question. Within each phase of the Perspective Plan, Perspective Plans, Development Plans, and Council Papers have been categorized for the benefit of future study and have been grouped together. The documents, which are the primary source of data for the investigation, are going to be presented in periodic pairings in the following part. Even though the Second Perspective Plan, which had its end date in 1995, had completed the last stage of development, the Seventh BYKP, which covered the years 1996-2000, was not included in the perspective plans since a new long-term plan was not prepared.

Despite the fact that the Second Perspective Plan had run its course by 1995, this was the situation.

The manner in which education is carried out determines whether or not it will have a direct or indirect impact on economic expansion. We can offer an example of the direct influence that education has on an individual's hourly wage, but we can also give an example of the indirect effect that education has by showing how it may increase the labor force participation rate, particularly among women. You may find both of these instances in the phrase that came before this one. It is also common knowledge that educated individuals have a beneficial impact on the productivity of other people, which leads to a rise not just in production levels but also in income levels. This phenomenon is known as the "education effect." The positive feedback loop created by educated individuals has led to this conclusion. Although the precise determination of the effects of education on social and economic growth will be the focus of a separate research project, it would be useful to briefly mention the effects of education on social and economic growth in order to gain a better understanding of the connection between education and growth in social and economic conditions. Because of this, a deeper knowledge of the connection between education and advancement will be provided. The overwhelming majority of economists who have focused their research on education are of the view that education is the bedrock upon which economic growth is constructed. One example that is brought up very often in this conversation is the manner in which nations located in the Far East have raised the amount of money they spend on education in order to cultivate human resources and advance economic growth. This is an example that gets brought up rather often in this conversation. Kim et al. found, in line with the findings of other studies for developed countries, that technological developments that increase productivity and lead to new products and production methods account for more than fifty percent of economic development. This finding is consistent with the findings of other studies for developed countries. In more recent times, some academics have started the practice of defining the volume of economic production as a function of the total quantity of human capital. The findings of these scholarly studies prove that the expansion of human capital is the single factor that contributes to total economic production. The term "human capital" refers to the knowledge that, once it has been created, may be put to use without the need of further monetary investment. It is a well-established truth that the most significant part in producing unique ideas is the combination of an existing knowledge base and a human capital pool that already exists. An increase in education level by one year is believed to result in an increase in private rate of return that is between 5 and 15 percentage points higher and an increase in productivity per employee that is 20 percentage

points higher, according to a number of studies. According to the findings of several studies, economic disparities are also associated with differences in productivity, which are the direct outcome of variations in levels of educational attainment.

6. The Relationship Between Human Resources and Growth

The findings of Wheeler's model, which studies the link between human resources and development and encompasses 88 developing nations, reveal that an increase in literacy from 20 percent to 30 percent raises gross domestic product from 8 percent to 16 percent. The model investigates the connection between growth and the availability of human resources. Wheeler's approach examines the connection that exists between expansion and the availability of human resources. It has also been set up that the rate of return on investment in education at the tertiary level delivers a pretty high rate of return, which is helpful not just to the individual but to society as a whole. This is an example of a benefit. At this point in time, it is common knowledge that the cultivation of human capital in a manner that is consistent with the aims of development has a beneficial impact, not only on the rate of economic growth but also on the quality of employment possibilities. It shouldn't come as much of a surprise that the benefits of education extend much beyond the benefits connected with straightforward economic growth and increased output levels. The most significant benefits that an education may support people are an enhancement of their overall quality of life as well as the opportunity to become useful contributors to their communities. This is the single most valuable contribution that education is capable of making. In addition to these advantages, education also serves to improve health, environmental consciousness, and per capita income; decreases crime, poverty, and inequality; contributes to the growth of democracy and the upkeep of political stability; and keeps political order.

7. Higher Education System Before Implementation of the Development Plan

The name of the institution, which had previously been referred to as Darülfünun-u Osmani, was changed to Istanbul Darülfünun by a statute that was passed in 1924, shortly after the Republic of Turkey was set up. The first university to be created following the fall of the Ottoman Empire was given administrative and academic autonomy in a circular that was issued in 1925. This gave the institution full control over its operations. The government of the Ottoman empire allowed for this level of autonomy. 1924 was the year that saw the establishment of this organization for the first time. In 1932, it was decided that Darülfun was unable to meet the commitments that were needed from him. As a result, Albert Malche, a

professor at Swiss Golf University, was assigned to help Darülfünun in meeting these obligations. In order for the institution to make headway, Albert Malche was given the responsibility of doing study on the appropriate procedures that should be adhered to. As a direct consequence of the findings presented in Malche's study in 1933, Istanbul Darülfünun was reorganized into what is now known as Istanbul University. In 1933, the university's autonomy was removed, the institution was brought under the authority of the Government of National Education, and the ministry was given the responsibility of selecting new rectors for the university. All of these events took place simultaneously. As a consequence of the modifications that took place in 1944, the educational establishment that had first been established in 1773 under the name Muhendishane-i Berri Hümayun was afterwards given the name Istanbul Technical University. For the very first time, several political parties were granted permission to take part in day-to-day operations when the Universities Act was ratified and passed into law in 1946. Mektep-i Mektep, which had been formed in 1925, Gazi Education Institute, which had been set up in 1926, and Higher Agricultural Institute, which had been set up in 1933 were all included into the newly established organization as a direct consequence of this legislation. The University of Ankara The reform of the university that was conducted in 1946 resulted in the revocation of the autonomy that had been granted in 1933, the establishment of the legal personality of the faculties, and the beginning of the implementation of the dependence on the budget. On the other hand, for the whole of this process to reform higher education, no legislation was drafted to oversee the planning, coordination, or oversight of higher education institutions. Both Karadeniz Technical University (KTU) and Ege University had their starts in the academic world in the same year, 1955. It wasn't until 1957 and 1959, respectively, that Atatürk University and Middle East Technical University opened their doors to students. Before this time, there were only three universities in Turkey; however, beginning in the 1950s, establishments that were situated in sections of the country that were not considered to be its primary metropolitan districts started to open their doors. As a direct consequence of this, there are now a total of seven universities in Turkey. In 1958, the Ministry of National Education gave KTU and Ege Universities the autonomy status that allowed them to run independently from the institutions in Ankara and Istanbul that the ministry oversaw. KTU and Ege Universities were both created inside the universities in those cities. The Ministry of National Education handles founding both of these prestigious educational institutions. In an analogous manner, Atatürk University, which is thought to deal with the issues of farmers, builders, manufacturers, workers, and businessmen in various fields as well as traditional professions, remained under the management of the Ministry of National Education until 1976 and then the

Ministry of National Education in 1976. This was because Atatürk University was thought to deal with the issues of farmers, builders, manufacturers, workers, and businesspeople in various fields. By electing its own rector, it developed into an independent academic institution. It is generally accepted that Atatürk University is concerned with the issues that are faced by farmers, builders, manufacturers, laborers, and businesses in a variety of disciplines, in addition to conventional professions. It is expected that the interests of farmers, builders, manufacturers, laborers, and dealers in many areas as well as traditional professions would be served by Ataturk University. It is believed that students typically concentrate on general education subfields, while instruction continues at the theoretical level in vocational and technical higher education. There are a total of 166 higher education institutions in the country. These institutions include 19 universities, 13 engineering and architecture academies, 6 economic and commercial sciences academies, 1 state academy of fine arts, 108 institutions affiliated with the Ministry of National Education and Science, and other 19 institutions affiliated with other ministries. In addition, there were 19 institutes that were connected to several other ministries. It was decided to do this in order to get rid of the many circumstances and disconnections that had happened. All institutes of higher education were consolidated into 27 universities in accordance with Legislation No. 2547, which came into effect on November 4, 1981; the YOK, which was founded as a result of this law, will ensure that resources are used in an effective and strategic manner; As a result of this situation, all institutions of higher education were reorganized into regionalized systems, and the academic staff shortage was eventually eliminated. The academic staff gap was filled with the release of 7,265 faculty members. Ninety percent of faculty members are concentrated in eight advanced universities. It was not possible to create attractive conditions that would encourage bright students to enter the university; it is not possible to plan higher education from a long-term perspective; the continued establishment of new higher education institutions despite the absence of proper educational and vocational preparation conditions. The rate of schooling, which had been approximately 10 percent up until 1979 but had dropped to 8 percent by the time the plan era came to a close, was caused by the inadequate completion of research efforts. This reduction is due to the inadequate completion of research efforts, which is the reason why. In only one year, the number of students attending educational institutions went from 100,000 to 10,000 less. Since 1963, development plans have been created for periods of five years at a time, and yearly programs have been devised to serve as the plans' implementation periods. Both of these practices date back to 1963. In addition to the planning of all other social and economic sectors, planning also encompasses the planning of the sector about higher education. As a direct consequence of

implementing these tactics, the attainment of economic and social advancement is the desired end result. The country's economic and social levels have progressed quickly as a direct consequence of the enhancements that have been done in the expected period to increase the level and quality of education. These advancements were conducted in the allotted amount of time. If we give the important shifts in education indices throughout the course of the projection period only a quick check, we will notice the following: The literacy rate increased from 39.5% in the year 1960 to 86.6% in the year 2001; the number of students enrolled in higher education increased from 61,000 in the year 1961 to 1,664,000 in the year 2001; the number of teaching staff increased from 4,071 in the year 1961 to 70,012 in the year 2002; the number of students enrolled in higher education increased from 61,000 in the year 1961 to 1,664,000 in the year 2001. When there were only 49 faculties, institutes, and colleges in 1960, there were 1,667 of them in 2002; when there were only 7 universities in 1960, there were 77 of them in 2002; the total number of educational institutions more than tripled between 1960 and 2002. Comparatively, the number of students who were enrolled in higher education in the year 2001 was the same as the rate of enrolment in higher education which was 4.1 percent in the year 1961. As a consequence of strong growth rates, the national income per capita went from being 542 dollars at the end of the Plan era to being 3000 dollars at the conclusion of the 7th Plan period, and it was over 6000 dollars when purchasing power parity was taken into account. This rise may be traced back to the robust growth rates that the economy has been able to reach in recent years. This is a really significant advance. Agriculture was the source of more than 40 percent of the total income received by the government before the adoption of the plan. On the other hand, by the time the 7th Plan had run its course, this figure had dropped to 13 percent. It is impossible to understate the significance of the contribution made by the expansion of human capital, which has come about as a direct consequence of the expansion of educational possibilities, to the advancements that have taken place in the economy. In point of fact, according to the studies that were carried out by specialists, it was found that education makes a significant contribution to the betterment of both social and economic situations, and these findings have been disclosed. More information on the fundamental tenets and overarching goals of each plan, as well as the steps that need to be followed to put each plan into motion, may be found in the section that was just read. In addition, the table that follows supplies an overview of the plans' aims and goals, as well as an evaluation of where they are in terms of implementation:

It is especially important to make a decision right away. This is something that needs to be said clearly and at once. It is important that this be brought to everyone's attention as soon

as possible. This is because the baseline analysis does not take into account every change that occurs during the plan period. Rather, their purpose is to explain a concept by making complex material easier to understand in order to further enhance understanding.

Human capital, as opposed to physical capital, is the part that will supply growth and structural change in the realization of socioeconomic development, according to those who defend the theory of human capital. Those who defend the theory of human capital are known as human capital advocates. This stands in stark contrast to the reality that physical capital is the part that will manage bringing about these transformations. Many individuals are of the opinion that receiving an education is one of the most significant ways to build up one's human capital. On the other hand, it is a well-established truth that not all degrees of education have the same impact on the expansion of the economy. This is something that has been recognized for an exceptionally long time. As more time passes and the economy continues to expand, there will be an increased need for educated individuals who are able to work in a wide range of professions and vocations. At the beginning of the industrialization process in a society, there is a greater focus put on vocational education than at any other period. Earlier on in development, a greater focus was put on general education as a means of constructing an infrastructure. Nevertheless, when a society first starts the process of industrialization, this is the period at which greater emphasis is put on vocational education and training. It is possible that integrating academic study with work experience in the real world might serve as a form of "growth accelerator" for companies and economies. In order to cultivate a labor force that has the necessary levels of knowledge and experience, developing nations like Turkey need to place a greater emphasis and priority on education that is more vocational and technical in nature.

Turkey, which has been seeking full membership in the European Union for a considerable amount of time, has been exerting a substantial amount of effort in this direction for some time now. This has been the case for some time now. Before setting up a system of vocational education that is best suited to meet its own requirements, Turkey should first carefully evaluate the Union's vision for vocational and technical education. After that, it should investigate other countries that have diverse types of vocational education systems. The primary aim of this research is to analyze the nature, degree, and direction of the link between vocational and technical education and the expansion of the economy in Turkey. This will be conducted via the use of both qualitative and quantitative methods. The VAR model was used in this investigation to discover whether or not there is a connection between Turkey's Gross Domestic

Product (GDP) and GDP Per Capita (GDP) and the number of students who are enrolled in Turkey's primary, secondary, higher, and vocational education systems. This investigation was conducted in order to ascertain whether or not these two factors are connected to one another in any way. According to the findings of the study, education-related indicators and the Basic Gross Domestic Product (KBGDP) are interwoven. In addition, there is a Granger causation link that runs in both ways between various levels of educational attainment and GDP or KBGDP. This relationship holds true regardless of the degree of educational attainment. Both the decomposition of variance and the impulse-response analysis supplied results that were equivalent in highlighting the significance of education, and more specifically vocational and technical education, in offering an explanation for growth.

These results brought to light the significance of education as a potential factor in the increase of populations. As the relevance of information and communication technology continues to rise, it is a well-established fact that increasing the number of people with specialized skills makes a substantial contribution to the expansion of the economy. This is particularly true when taking into consideration the growing significance of information and communication technology. One of the most fundamental differences that can be drawn between industrialized nations and developing countries is the degree to which a nation's workforce is educated and trained in all relevant subjects. This is one of the most crucial contrasts that can be drawn. When it comes to deciding the level of productivity that may be achieved by a workforce, education is the most crucial factor to take into consideration. Both economically and socially, education is one of the most essential resources that may be used throughout the process of growth. The provision of educational opportunities is among the most essential resources. A person's positive qualities, such as their education, skills, experience, and even their level of energy, all contribute to the individual's overall human quality and are considered to be part of their "human capital." One of the most fundamental aspects of human capital is a person's level of education. The terms "knowledge," "skills," "experience," and "dynamism" are all examples of intangible assets that make up "human capital." ("Which of these does not constitute human capital?") The process of development makes use of a wide range of resources, but human capital stands out as one of the most essential of them. The distinction between education and other essential components of the development process is not only significant from an economic standpoint; it also has the potential to function as a compass for directing these processes in terms of the social ramifications they may have. Among the many aspects that contribute, education stands out as particularly important. In recent years, the idea that education bears growing weight in terms of its influence on the socioeconomic progress of

nations has arisen. This notion is based on the observation that education tends to become better with time. The expansion of the economy is just one aspect of development; taking into account the structural and intellectual shifts occurring in a variety of fields, which are at least as important as the expansion of the economy, it is both general education and vocational and technical education that will provide this.

On the other hand, not all forms of education supply the same results in terms of how quickly the economy expands, and this is a truth that is both well-documented and generally acknowledged. When a society has just recently begun the process of industrialization, the significance of general education starts to decline while the value of vocational and technical education begins to rise.

8. Conclusion

In the early phases of development, the establishment of an infrastructure is the responsibility of general education. As opposed to general education, vocational education is the form of education that, in this context, is used in the creation and development of industry that contributes to economic growth as well as the manufacture and advancement of key inventions. The primary aim of vocational and technical education is to provide students with instruction in the correct application of a variety of technologies and to implant in them the fundamental knowledge and abilities that are needed for a certain field of endeavor. In addition, the goal of vocational and technical education is to get students ready for jobs in the workforce in lower-level positions. As a consequence of this, these participants are able to join the labor market in a professional capacity that is more suited for them, and the demands of the firms in terms of intermediate employees are addressed. In order to cultivate a labor force that has the necessary levels of knowledge and experience, developing nations like Turkey need to place a greater emphasis and priority on education that is more vocational and technical in nature. Career and technical education may be seen as a form of stimulant for the acceleration of economic growth because of the growing significance it has with the development of the economy. In this light, it is important to note that, during the last few years in Turkey, there has been an expansion in the number of programs and activities that are geared at supplying vocational and technical education. Taking into account this pattern is important.

9. References

- Kaul, Inge and Mendoza, RU (2003). Advancing the Concept of Public Goods. Published Book I.Kaul, P. Conceicao, K. Le Goulven and RUMendoza (Editors), Supplying Global Public Goods: Managing Globalization (78-111). USA: Oxford University Press.
- Kucuker, Erdal. (2008). Analysis of Education Plans Made in the Scope of Development Plans (1963-2005). Unpublished Doctoral Thesis. Ankara University Institute of Educational Sciences, Ankara.
- McMahon, Walter W. (1999). Education and Development: Measuring the Social Benefits. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Happy, Aysegul. (1998). Evaluation of Consolidated Budget Expenditures in Turkey 1981-1985. 12.Turkey Finance Symposium, 15-17 May 1997. Istanbul: Finance Research Center Publication No: 83.
- Ozguven, Ali. (1988). Economic Growth Economic Development Social Planning and Japanese Development. Istanbul: Filiz Bookstore.
- Aslaner, N. (2008). National Education Councils and education policies. (1939-1946) (Unpublished Master's Thesis). Gazi University, Ankara.
- Battal, Y. (2011). Change in development policies, regional development agencies (Unpublished PhD Thesis). Sakarya University, Sakarya.
- Amazigh, M. (2006). Economic growth and development. Trabzon: Derya Bookstore.
- Deniz, M. (2001). History of National Education Councils and its effects on education policies (Unpublished Master's Thesis). Suleyman Demirel University, Isparta.
- Duffy, B. (2014). The analysis of documentary evidence. In J. Bell (Eds.), Doing your research project: A guide for first-time researchers (pp. 125-140). UK: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Eroglu, A. (2001). Resources distributed to education in Turkey and the role of education in economic development (Unpublished Master's Thesis). Marmara University, Istanbul.
- Calcioglu, M. (1993). Planning studies in the education sector after 1980 in Turkey. M. U. Atatürk Faculty of Education Journal of Educational Sciences, 5, 59-66.
- Calcioglu, M. (2001). Human resources planning at macro level in Turkey. Ankara: Memoir Publishing.
- Kucuker, E. (2008). "Analysis of education plans made within the scope of

- Development Plans (1963-2005) (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis)." ("Theory and Practice in Education » Article » National Planned Development Period ...") Ankara University, Ankara.
- Kucuker, E. (2012). Analysis of education plans made within the scope of Development Plans in Turkey. *Kastamonu Journal of Education*, 20(1), 9-26.
- Paksoy, EE (2011). Evaluation of the applicability of the decisions of the National Education Council on the Development Plans: An examination in terms of vocational education. II. Educational Administration Forum, 22-23 October, Başkent Teacher's House, Ankara, Turkey.
- Seyidoglu, H. (1993). *International economics* (9th ed.). Istanbul: Gizem Publications.
- Turkmen, Fatih. *Economic and Social Benefits of Education and Investigation of the Relationship between Education and Economic Growth in Turkey*, SPO Specialization Thesis, Publication No. 2655, 2002.
- Ulukan, Emir. *Comparative Evaluation of Vocational Education Models Implemented in Turkey*, Ankara: TES-AR Publications, Publication No: 28, 1998.
- Ulusoy, Ayten. "Educational Institution-Business Cooperation in Training Qualified Workforce: Turkey Practice", *Employer Magazine*, TİSK, May 2004.
- Unay, Cafer. *The Effects of Education on Economic Development*, Istanbul: AR Publishing, October 1982.
- Uzun, Abdullah and Osman Eldoğan, "Overview of the Problems of Education in Vocational Schools, Policies and Strategies in Vocational and Technical Education", *International Conference on Challenges Awaiting Vocational Education and Training in Turkey in Terms of the EU Copenhagen Process and the Maastricht Declaration*. Ankara: MEB, 2005.
- Wadie, Mohammed Adnan. "Development Indexes: Theory and Measurement", *Research in Human Capital and Development*, London: Jai Press Inc, Volume 11A, 1997.
- Woodhall, M. "Educational Economics: An Overview", *Educational Economics: Selected Papers*. Translated by Yuksel Kavak, Berrin Burgaz. Ankara: Personnel Development Center Publication

No: 14, 1994. “The Concept of Human Capital”, Educational Economics: Selected Articles. Translators: Yüksel Kavak, Berrin Burgaz, Ankara: Personnel Development Center Publication No: 14, 1994.

Yavilioglu, Cengiz. “The Semantic History and Conceptual Origins of Development”, Cumhuriyet University Journal of FEAS. Volume no: 3, Issue no: 1, 2002.